

CORRECTIVE WORK ON THE FORMATION OF THE SYLLABIC STRUCTURE OF WORDS IN PRIMARY SCHOOL CHILDREN WITH SPEECH DISORDERS

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Annotation: The article examines the peculiarities of syllabic structure disorders in primary school children with severe speech disorders and ways of their correction. Based on the analysis of works by Russian researchers (G. V. Babina, A. K. Markova, N. Yu. Safonkina, S. E. Bolshakova, etc.), the main difficulties of children with speech disorders in mastering the syllabic structure of a word are revealed. The necessity of systematic and step-by-step speech therapy work using visual modeling methods, game technologies, and speech exercises is substantiated. The importance of forming the correct syllabic structure of a word for the successful acquisition of written speech and the prevention of dysgraphia and dyslexia is emphasized.

Keywords: syllabic word structure, speech disorders, general speech underdevelopment (GSU), phonemic perception, articulatory motor skills, correctional work, speech therapy practice; primary schoolchildren, sound-syllabic analysis, speech formation.

Introduction.

The formation of the syllabic structure of a word is one of the key components of a child's speech development. Normally, mastering the syllabic structure occurs gradually and is associated with the development of phonemic perception, auditory-verbal memory and articulatory motor skills. However, in children with severe speech impairments (SSI), this process is slow and is accompanied by numerous difficulties.

Research by G. V. Babina and N. Yu. Safonkina [1] shows that a violation of the syllabic structure is one of the most persistent speech defects in this category of children. A. K. Markova [3] notes that errors in the construction of the syllabic structure can persist until primary school age and hinder the successful acquisition of reading and writing. Thus, remedial work on the formation of the syllabic structure of a word in primary school children with SSI is particularly relevant and requires a comprehensive, step-by-step approach. The following types of disorders are most often encountered in primary school children with speech disorders:

- abbreviation of words (for example: "mashina" → mana);
- rearrangement of syllables (karandash → kadarash);
- simplification of consonant clusters (stol → tol);

- omissions or insertions of syllables;
- assimilation of syllables (repetition of one syllable instead of different ones).

According to observations of S. E. Bolshakova [2], such errors are caused by a combination of weak phonemic perception, underdevelopment of auditory-speech memory and difficulties in programming articulation. As a result, the child does not retain the integral structure of the word and disrupts its sound-syllabic composition. The main causes of syllabic structure disorders include: insufficient phonemic perception, poor development of speech memory, undeveloped articulatory motor skills, difficulties with language analysis and synthesis, and delayed formation of syllabic prosody (rhythm, stress, speech tempo). N. Yu. Safonkina [1] emphasizes that with speech impairment, syllabic structure disorders are systemic and require comprehensive correction.

To identify syllabic structure disorders, the following are used: G. V. Babina's method for diagnosing syllabic analysis and synthesis, S. E. Bolshakova's tasks for repeating words with different syllabic structures, R. I. Lalaeva's method for determining the number of syllables in a word, and speech therapy tests (repeat after an adult, name a picture, make a word out of syllables).

Diagnostics help identify the nature of errors and determine the direction of correctional work. Effective remedial work on the formation of the syllabic structure of a word should be step-by-step and include the following areas: development of phonemic perception, differentiation of sounds and syllables by ear, exercises to highlight the stressed syllable, games such as "Say the first syllable", "Clap the syllables", formation of syllabic analysis and synthesis, division of words into syllables using claps, steps, movements, composing words from the proposed syllables, using colored chips and cards, using visual modeling of a word diagram indicating the number of syllables, pictograms, cubes, chips for replacing sounds and syllables, work based on the principle of "from diagram to word", game methods and techniques, speech games ("Echo", "Chain of words"), speech rhythmization (poems, counting rhymes, claps), use of musical accompaniment, consolidation of the syllabic structure in coherent speech, inclusion of correctly constructed words in phrases and texts, as well as exercises in retelling and composing sentences. A.K. Markova [3] emphasizes that only systematic work with a gradual complication of the material allows achieving lasting positive results. Formation of the correct syllabic structure of a word is important for the speech and general development of a child. Firstly, it

promotes successful literacy. Secondly, it reduces the risk of dysgraphia and dyslexia. Thirdly, it creates the prerequisites for the full development of speech-thinking activity.

Violation of the syllabic structure of a word is one of the most persistent difficulties in primary school children with speech delay. Timely diagnostics and systematic correctional work, including the development of phonemic perception, the formation of syllabic analysis and synthesis, the use of visual modeling and game methods, can significantly increase the effectiveness of speech correction.

Reliance on the research of G. V. Babina, A. K. Markova, N. Yu. Safonkina, S. E. Bolshakova and other specialists confirms the need for an integrated approach. Formation of the correct syllabic structure of a word is not only a task of speech therapy practice, but also an important condition for the prevention of reading and writing disorders, which makes this area relevant both in theoretical and practical terms.

List of references:

1. Babina, G. V., Safonkina, N. Yu. Diagnostics and correction of syllabic structure disorders in children with general speech underdevelopment. — Moscow: Vldos, 2007. — 176 p.
2. Bolshakova, S. E. Formation of syllabic structure of words in children with speech disorders: a methodological manual. — St. Petersburg: Rech, 2005. — 128 p.
3. Markova, A. K. Correctional work on the formation of syllabic structure of words in children with speech impairment // Defectology. — 2012. — No. 3. — P. 15-21.
4. Bessonova, T. P. Russian language lessons in schools with severe speech impairments // Russian language in schools for children with severe speech impairments: a teaching aid / ed. A. A. Almazova, V. I. Seliverstov. - M.: Vldos, 2011. - P. 27-35.